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From Agitation To Insecurity: Assessing The Political Roots And Consequences Of Armed Struggle In South-East Nigeria, 2014–2024

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the impact of armed struggle on insecurity in South-East Nigeria from 2014 to 2024, situating the analysis within the context of the region's persistent political marginalization, poor governance, and structural injustice. Using a mixed-methods approach that combined survey data from 389 respondents with key informant interviews, the study explores how armed struggle has evolved as both a symptom and a driver of insecurity. Findings reveal that 384 respondents, with a mean score of 3.88, strongly agreed that armed struggle has led to the proliferation of arms and increased armed banditry. Insecurity has, in turn, undermined socioeconomic development, educational advancement, and human security, creating a vicious cycle of violence and deprivation. Empirical evidence from field data and interviews confirmed that the activities of groups such as the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) and the Eastern Security Network (ESN) have contributed to widespread displacement, migration, school closures, and loss of lives and livelihoods across the region. The study attributes these dynamics to governance failure, unemployment, political exclusion, and militarized state responses, which have collectively eroded public trust in government institutions. It concludes that without addressing the structural roots of the conflict, insecurity in the South-East will persist, undermining Nigeria's broader national stability. The study recommends inclusive governance, community-based peacebuilding initiatives, youth employment programmes, and demilitarization of the region as key measures for restoring peace and sustainable development.

Keywords: Armed Struggle, Governance, Insecurity, Marginalization, Peacebuilding, Politics, Security, South-East Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

The politics of marginalization, deprivation, neglect, human rights abuses, and structural imbalance, especially in state and local government creation—has continued to instigate numerous complex security challenges with significant humanitarian and economic consequences, leading to sectional agitations for secession in Nigeria (Egobueze, Ojirika, & Owaji-Ibani, 2021). The roots of insecurity in the South-East are deeply intertwined with the post-civil war socio-political context, where successive governments have failed to address the grievances of perceived exclusion and underrepresentation of the Igbo people. Since the end of the Nigerian Civil War in 1970, the people of Southeast Nigeria have consistently expressed feelings of marginalization in governance, resource distribution, and political appointments, resulting in a variety of movements calling for self-determination (Igwebuikwe, 2020; Okolie-Osemene & Ibeanu, 2023).

These grievances have created fertile ground for groups such as the Movement for the Actualization of the Sovereign State of Biafra (MASSOB) and the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) to emerge as vehicles of resistance and identity assertion. The renewed agitation for secession since 2014 reflects both historical memory and the contemporary realities of exclusion and bad governance (Ojukwu & Onuoha, 2021). The sit-at-home orders, protests, and violent confrontations that have characterized the South-East since 2021 have severely disrupted economic activities, education, and inter-regional trade. As Ekechukwu, Nwogu, Ugwukwu, and Emerho (2022) observe, these security crises have crippled the economy of the region, reducing productivity and investor confidence while heightening humanitarian suffering.

Similarly, Obi (2020) notes that Nigeria's political landscape remains marred by systemic inequalities, ethnic polarization, and governance deficits that exacerbate tensions between the federal government and various ethno-regional groups. This persistent imbalance has translated into widespread perceptions of injustice and alienation, driving separatist narratives. These political inadequacies manifested through nepotism, uneven infrastructural development, and skewed political appointments have created an enduring sense of exclusion, prompting the Southeast's demands for self-determination through groups like MASSOB, IPOB, and the Eastern Security Network (ESN) (Ude, 2022). Such prolonged agitations have eroded national cohesion and undermined trust in federal institutions, leading to a cycle of violence and counter-violence that deepens insecurity.

The rhetoric of exclusion and marginalization championed by these movements has further polarized Nigeria's ethno-political space. Government responses have largely been coercive through militarization, arrests, and proscription of separatist organizations. The federal government's decision to label IPOB as a terrorist organization in 2017 under the Terrorism (Prevention) (Amendment) Act of 2013 further deepened mistrust between the region and the center (Anele, 2020; Okenwa & Onuoha, 2021). This designation polarized public opinion, undermined opportunities for constructive dialogue, and entrenched perceptions of political victimization. As Nwankwo (2023) contends, the government's approach, rooted in securitization rather than reconciliation, has escalated hostilities and legitimized violent resistance among some aggrieved youth.

The continuous clashes between IPOB supporters and Nigerian security forces have fostered a climate of mistrust and animosity, not only within the Southeast but also across the nation. Despite Nigeria's federal structure, the unequal distribution of power and resources persists, reinforcing IPOB's conviction that the region cannot achieve justice within the existing political framework. This deep-seated belief has sustained the demand for secession as a last resort for survival and dignity (Ibeanu & Okeke, 2021). Insecurity in the Southeast is therefore both a cause and consequence of political exclusion; armed struggle feeds on marginalization, while state repression amplifies militancy.

In addressing these tensions, the Nigerian government has employed a multifaceted strategy such as legal proscription, security crackdowns, and limited political engagement. Security operations, such as "Python Dance II" and "Golden Dawn," were launched to quell agitation but often resulted in civilian casualties and allegations of human rights abuses (Amnesty International, 2022). These operations, while intended to restore order, inadvertently inflamed resentment by perpetuating the narrative of oppression. Simultaneously, political rhetoric emphasizing unity without justice has failed to inspire confidence among the Southeast populace (Eke, 2022).

According to Onuoha and Okenwa (2021), the government has failed to adopt "advanced diplomacy" or genuine federal dialogue; instead, it relies heavily on coercive tactics that alienate affected communities. This approach, they argue, reveals a deliberate unwillingness to address the structural issues of marginalization, deprivation, and neglect. The government's military-centric response has resulted in significant socio-economic losses, including over ₦7.6 trillion in damages, more than 900 fatalities, and disruptions to education, local governance, and livelihoods (Obi, 2020; International Crisis Group, 2023). Such conditions further deepen the humanitarian crisis, creating a vicious cycle of violence, fear, and economic stagnation.

Empirical studies show that insecurity in the Southeast is strongly correlated with the rise of armed struggle. Nwachukwu (2022) and Ogbonna (2023) identify a feedback relationship between perceived injustice and violent mobilization: the more the state represses, the stronger the resolve of separatist groups to resist. This cycle of provocation and reprisal has transformed local grievances into a broader political and security challenge. The Southeast, once a hub of commerce and education, now faces

declining school enrollment, migration of businesses, and rising poverty conditions that further sustain armed militancy and criminal opportunism (Udeh & Nnoli, 2022).

Furthermore, human rights organizations and conflict analysts have noted that Nigeria's approach undermines long-term peacebuilding. Amnesty International (2022) and Human Rights Watch (2023) document patterns of extrajudicial killings, arbitrary detentions, and media repression targeting pro-Biafra activists. Such actions have delegitimized the state's moral authority and alienated moderate voices who could otherwise mediate between the government and agitators. The result is an increasingly fragmented Southeast where armed groups, criminal gangs, and vigilantes operate in blurred boundaries between political protest and organized crime.

Theoretically, the relationship between armed struggle and insecurity in Southeast Nigeria aligns with Gurr's (1970) Relative Deprivation Theory and Ted Robert Gurr's frustration-aggression hypothesis, which posit that political violence emerges when individuals or groups perceive a gap between expected and actual outcomes. The Southeast's agitation thus reflects accumulated frustration from decades of socio-economic and political exclusion. Similarly, Collier and Hoeffler's (2004) greed-grievance model provides insight into how both material and identity-based motivations fuel armed conflict in resource-limited settings.

However, scholars such as Ikelegbe (2021) and Alao (2020) emphasize that resolving such crises requires more than security operations, it demands systemic reforms in governance, equity, and representation. Inclusive dialogue and power devolution under a true federal framework could mitigate separatist tendencies and enhance national integration. The adoption of community-driven peace initiatives and transitional justice mechanisms would further address historical wounds and restore trust in the state.

In sum, the relationship between armed struggle and insecurity in Southeast Nigeria is cyclical and mutually reinforcing. Political exclusion, poor governance, and structural injustice fuel agitation, while militarized state responses intensify insecurity and radicalization. The Southeast crisis thus reflects the broader Nigerian paradox—where diversity, if mismanaged, becomes a source of division rather than strength. The pathway to peace lies not in repression but in the reconstruction of a just, inclusive, and accountable political order that restores citizens' confidence in the state. Based on this, the paper seeks to address a central research question thus: *what is the relationship between armed struggle and insecurity in South-East, Nigeria?*

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Relative Deprivation Theory explains collective unrest by focusing on how people **perceive** the gap between what they believe they deserve and what they actually receive. Its intellectual roots lie in Samuel A. Stouffer's empirical work on soldiers' attitudes during World War II (Stouffer et al., 1949), and the concept was developed into a general theory of political violence by Ted R. Gurr in *Why Men Rebel* (Gurr, 1970/2011). Gurr defines relative deprivation as the perceived discrepancy between value expectations and value capabilities; when expectations exceed capabilities, frustration grows and the risk of political violence increases.

The analytic power of the theory is that it locates the motivation for collective action in comparative perceptions rather than absolute levels of poverty. In other words, people riot, rebel, or join armed movements not only because they are poor, but because they see others enjoying privileges or opportunities they believe rightfully belong to them — or because state promises raise expectations that are later frustrated. This emphasis on perceived injustice explains why communities with similar objective conditions may diverge dramatically in their propensity to mobilize.

Applied to Nigeria, relative deprivation helps explain several region-specific insurgencies. In the oil-producing Niger Delta, for example, perceptions that communities shoulder environmental costs but are excluded from oil rents motivated militant agitation in the 1990s and 2000s (Moses & Olaniyi, 2017; Ikelegbe, 2006). The Niger Delta case illustrates how perceived distributional injustice, coupled with visible wealth elsewhere, catalyses violent mobilisation. Likewise, analyses linking relative deprivation to Nigeria's broader national insecurity show positive correlations between perceived exclusion and propensity to engage in violent protest.

In the South-East, the theory is particularly illuminating. The region's collective memory of wartime trauma, post-war reconstruction promises, and continuing perceptions of political under-representation and skewed resource allocation produce a powerful sense of comparative grievance.

Groups such as MASSOB and IPOB have channelled these perceptions into political mobilization and in some instances armed resistance. Relative deprivation explains why many in the South-East interpret their socio-political status not as isolated hardship but as relative injustice compared to other regions that appear to receive disproportionate political appointments, federal projects, or infrastructural investment.

The theory’s usefulness extends to understanding the mobilisation processes: perceived deprivation alone does not automatically result in violence. The transformation of grievance into collective action requires organizational frames, leadership, and opportunity structures. In Nigeria these include charismatic leaders, diasporic networks, local vigilante formations, and permissive security vacuums; these enable grievances to be politicized and militarized. Thus, relative deprivation identifies the psychological trigger, but other triggers such as leadership, institutions, and resource opportunities that explain why some grievances escalate while others do not.

Critics of the theory note two limitations. First, it tends to over-privilege perception at the expense of structural factors: historical institutional arrangements, legal discrimination, and formal exclusion also shape outcomes. Second, empirical tests show that perceived deprivation is a necessary but not sufficient condition for rebellion—many deprived groups never mobilize violently. Researchers therefore often combine relative deprivation with structural or rational-choice explanations (e.g., greed vs. grievance, horizontal inequalities) to capture causal complexity. Nevertheless, relative deprivation remains a valuable interpretive lens for explaining why people respond violently to perceived inequality even when absolute deprivation is ambiguous.

For this paper, relative deprivation is an apt theoretical anchor. It highlights how subjective feelings of exclusion over political appointments, state creation, federal projects, and resource distribution can translate into collective action and, under certain conditions, armed struggle. The theory explains why South-East mobilization is not reducible to raw poverty: it is about dignity, recognition, and fairness in a federal arrangement perceived as inequitable. A policy implication flowing from this framing is clear: reducing conflict requires measures that close expectation-capability gaps (through inclusive governance, equitable resource sharing, and credible reconciliation), not only short-term security suppression.

The theoretical model of perceived grievances and conflicts in South - Eastern Nigeria is as presented in the figure below:

Figure 1. Theoretical model of the relationship between perceived grievances and violence in South-East Nigeria

METHODOLOGY

This research employed a mixed-methods approach, combining both qualitative and quantitative strategies to generate a comprehensive understanding of how political dynamics influence armed

struggles in South-East Nigeria. The integration of these two methods enabled triangulation of data, ensuring reliability, validity, and depth of insight. The qualitative dimension relied on structured interviews designed to elicit participants' lived experiences and perceptions, while the quantitative component utilized structured questionnaires and Chi-square (χ^2) statistical analysis to determine the nature and significance of relationships among key variables. Secondary sources like including books, peer-reviewed journals, and official government publications were also incorporated to provide historical and contextual grounding. This methodological framework was considered most suitable for identifying the interconnections between political activities, structural grievances, and the escalation of armed conflict in the region.

The population of the study encompassed all residents across the five states, totaling 22,012,828 people (NBS, 2024). Using Taro Yamane's formula at a 5% margin of error, a sample size of 400 respondents was determined. A multi-stage sampling technique ensured proportional representation across states and stakeholder categories, namely youths, community leaders, NGO officials, and security personnel with 80 questionnaires distributed per state.

Data collection involved both primary and secondary sources. Primary data came from structured questionnaires designed on a 4-point Likert scale, complemented by semi-structured interviews. The principal instrument, titled the Politics and Armed Struggle Questionnaire (PAS-Q), comprised six sections (A–F), covering demographic information, causes of armed struggle, its socio-political impact, and government responses. Content and face validity were ensured through expert review and peer evaluation, while a pilot study confirmed clarity and usability. Instrument reliability was verified through repeated expert assessments, achieving a consistency coefficient above 0.90, signifying strong dependability.

For analysis, descriptive statistics (mean and percentage) summarized responses, while inferential statistics, specifically the Chi-square (χ^2) test, were employed to test hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. Responses with mean scores of 2.5 or above were accepted as statistically significant. Results were presented using tables, charts, and frequency distributions to facilitate clear interpretation and meaningful discussion of findings.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

This section presents and analyzes the data obtained from the field. It is divided into two parts. The first part discusses the demographic characteristics of respondents and the overall questionnaire response rate, while the second part analyzes responses to the key research questions using mean scores and hypothesis testing. The findings are interpreted in relation to the study's objectives.

Presentation of Data

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Analysis of Response Rate

Administration of Questionnaires	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Number of questionnaires administered	400	100
Number of questionnaires not returned	11	3
Number of questionnaires retrieved	389	97
Number of questionnaires valid for the study	389	97

Source: *Fieldwork*, 2025.

The data in Table 1 show that out of the 400 questionnaires administered, 389 were successfully retrieved and found valid for analysis, representing a 97% response rate. Only 11 questionnaires, constituting 3%, were not returned. A 97% completion rate indicates a high level of participation and reliability of the data, demonstrating effective field engagement and strong respondent cooperation.

Table 2: Response Rate by Stakeholder Category

Category	Questionnaires Distributed	Questionnaires Returned
Youth Groups	100	98
Community Leaders	100	98
NGOs	100	97
Security Agents	100	96
Total	400	389

Source: *Fieldwork*, 2025.

Table 2 illustrates the distribution and retrieval of questionnaires across stakeholder groups. Out of 100 questionnaires administered to each group, youth groups and community leaders each returned 98, while NGOs and security agents returned 97 and 96 respectively. This balanced distribution reflects a broad and inclusive representation of perspectives relevant to politics and armed struggle in South-East Nigeria. The overall response rate of 97% confirms the robustness of the data collected.

Table 3: Gender Distribution of Respondents

Gender	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Male	220	57
Female	169	43
Total	389	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2025.

As shown in Table 3, male respondents constituted 57% of the sample, while female respondents accounted for 43%. Although there is a slightly higher male representation, the difference does not significantly affect the study outcomes since both genders provided diverse yet objective views on the subject matter.

Table 4: Educational Background of Respondents

Educational Qualification	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
PSLC/SSCE	100	26
HND/BSc/PGD	200	51
MSc/MPA/MBA/PhD	89	23
Total	389	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2025.

Table 4 reveals that most respondents possess post-secondary education. Specifically, 26% hold PSLC/SSCE, 51% have HND/BSc/PGD, and 23% possess postgraduate qualifications (MSc/MPA/MBA/PhD). The predominance of respondents with tertiary education suggests a well-informed sample capable of providing insightful and credible opinions on political and security issues in the South-East region. Their educational attainment enhances the reliability of the data and the depth of analysis.

The demographic data presented confirm that responses were obtained from a diverse and educated population across stakeholder groups. The high response rate and balanced gender distribution strengthen the validity of the research findings. The next section presents analysis based on mean scores, Chi-square tests, and hypothesis verification to determine the relationship between political activities and armed struggle in South-East Nigeria.

DATA ANALYSIS

Research Question: What is the relationship between armed struggle and insecurity in South-East Nigeria?

This section analyzes respondents' views on how armed struggle relates to the rising insecurity in the South-East region of Nigeria. Data were collected from four key stakeholder groups such as youths, community development committee (CDC) members, non-governmental organization (NGO) representatives, and security agents. These were summarized in Tables 4.10 to 4.14. The results are discussed accordingly.

Table 5: Armed Struggle and the Armament of Banditry in South-East Nigeria

Options	Youth	CDC	NGO	Security Agent	Total	Response Mean Value	Remark
Strongly Agreed (4)	85	90	95	80	350		
Agreed (3)	10	8	1	15	34		
Disagreed (2)	3	0	1	0	4		
Strongly Disagreed (1)	0	0	0	1	1	3.88	Accepted
Total	98	98	97	96	389		

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 5 shows that a majority (350) of the respondents strongly agreed that armed struggle has resulted in the armament of armed banditry in the South-East. Another 34 respondents agreed, while only 5 respondents disagreed to varying degrees. The mean score of 3.88 confirms a strong consensus that armed struggle has intensified insecurity through the proliferation of arms and bandit activities in the region.

Table 6: Impact of Armed Struggle on Socioeconomic Development

Options	Youth	CDC	NGO	Security Agent	Total Response	Mean Value	Remark
Strongly Agreed (4)	82	68	72	80	302		
Agreed (3)	16	24	18	10	68		
Disagreed (2)	0	5	4	4	13		
Strongly Disagreed (1)	0	1	3	2	6	3.71	Accepted
Total	98	98	97	96	389		

Source: Field Survey, 2025

As shown in Table 6, 302 respondents strongly agreed that insecurity driven by armed struggle has negatively affected socioeconomic development in the South-East. A further 68 respondents agreed, while only 19 disagreed. With a mean score of 3.71, it is evident that insecurity has disrupted livelihoods, discouraged investment, and hindered economic activities across affected communities.

Table 7: Armed Struggle, Insecurity, and Educational Development

Options	Youth	CDC	NGO	Security Agent	Total Response	Mean Value	Remark
Strongly Agreed (4)	64	66	74	62	266		
Agreed (3)	31	29	19	32	111		
Disagreed (2)	2	1	3	2	8		
Strongly Disagreed (1)	1	2	1	0	4	3.64	Accepted
Total	98	98	97	96	389		

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 7 reveals that 266 respondents strongly agreed that armed struggle and insecurity have caused a setback in educational development in the South-East. An additional 111 respondents agreed, while only 12 opposed the statement. The mean value of 3.64 reinforces that educational institutions have been severely disrupted — with frequent closures, reduced student attendance, and migration of teachers due to security threats.

Table 8: Migration and Displacement Due to Insecurity

Options	Youth	CDC	NGO	Security Agent	Total Response	Mean Value	Remark
Strongly Agreed (4)	94	93	89	20	296		
Agreed (3)	4	5	6	30	45		
Disagreed (2)	0	0	2	30	32		
Strongly Disagreed (1)	0	0	0	16	16	3.60	Accepted
Total	98	98	97	96	389		

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 8 indicates that 296 respondents strongly agreed that insecurity from armed struggle has caused unwarranted migration and displacement in the South-East. This trend is especially visible in rural communities where fear of violence forces families to relocate. The mean score of 3.60 confirms that displacement has become a major humanitarian concern linked to ongoing armed conflicts and separatist activities in the region.

Table 9: Insecurity and the Loss of Lives

Options	Youth	CDC	NGO	Security Agent	Total	Response	Mean Value	Remark
Strongly Agreed (4)	86	76	73	45	280			
Agreed (3)	9	17	17	5	48			
Disagreed (2)	1	2	5	45	53			
Strongly Disagreed (1)	2	3	2	1	8		3.54	Accepted
Total	98	98	97	96	389			

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The results from Table 4.14 show that 280 respondents strongly agreed that insecurity has resulted in the death of many people across the South-East. Another 48 respondents agreed, while 61 disagreed. Despite some dissenting views, the mean score of 3.54 supports the conclusion that armed confrontations, extrajudicial killings, and communal clashes have contributed significantly to the loss of lives in the region.

Summary of Findings for Research Question Two

The findings collectively indicate a strong positive relationship between armed struggle and insecurity in South-East Nigeria. Respondents widely agreed that armed struggle has escalated violence through:

1. Increased banditry and arms proliferation;
2. Decline in socioeconomic activities and local investment;
3. Severe disruption of education and schooling;
4. Mass displacement and internal migration; and
5. Significant loss of human lives.

All five items recorded mean scores above 3.50, indicating strong agreement across categories of respondents. This shows that the consequences of armed struggle in the South-East transcend mere political agitation. They have evolved into multifaceted security, social, and economic crises that threaten regional stability and development.

Investigating the Impact of Armed Struggle on Insecurity in South-East Nigeria

Primary data revealed that 384 respondents, with a mean score of 3.88, agreed that armed struggle has led to the armament of banditry and general insecurity in the South-East. Secondary data also indicated that the proliferation of arms among various armed groups has increased the rate of violent crimes such as armed robbery, kidnapping, cultism, and political violence in the region. The absence of peace, rule of law, and a predictable social order has consequently undermined human productivity and economic activities.

According to one interviewee:

Armed struggle has led to the formation of different youth groups and the proliferation of arms in the region. The role of these groups in the South-East has had several negative implications on the social, economic, educational, political, and security landscapes of Nigeria. The negative activities of these groups have also led to the death of social life—night parties, clubbing, and outdoor worship are disappearing due to fear and intimidation by these armed groups

(O. Nwite, personal communication, February 4, 2025).

This finding aligns with Ezemenaka (2021), who argued that the failure of governance and statehood in Nigeria has bred an anarchical and disruptive system that legitimizes youth violence and anti-state behavior. Similarly, Uzoagu (2022) maintained that insecurity and youth restiveness often originate from the political manipulation of armed conflict and ethnic grievances. Pettinger (2017) observed that youth restiveness negatively affects community security, economic activity, and personal development. Furthermore, Yusuf (2013) highlighted that armament and violence are often products of poor governance, unemployment, exclusion from political participation, and lack of social amenities, factors that lead to criminality, insecurity, and underdevelopment (Akpokighe & Ejovi, 2020).

Data analysis also revealed that 302 respondents, with a mean score of 3.71, agreed that insecurity has negatively affected socioeconomic development in the region. One respondent stated:

When there is conflict, the environment is no longer conducive for socioeconomic development. The conflict has led to unemployment, out-of-school children, poverty,

and lack of investment. The sit-at-home order has reduced the region to an insignificant marketplace. Some youths have hijacked IPOB's cause to commit robbery and murder. I was falsely accused of being an IPOB member, tortured by the military, and lost my job as a result. Losing one's livelihood to insecurity is devastating (P. Okafor, personal communication, February 7, 2025).

In support of this, Okafor (2020) explained that persistent conflict in the South-East has perpetuated poverty, unemployment, and underdevelopment. The emergence of groups such as the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) and the Eastern Security Network (ESN) has further amplified grievances of economic marginalization (Eze, 2021). Similarly, Igbo and Ikpa (2013) linked armed struggle to poor government policies, unemployment, and inadequate educational systems. Ifidon and Ahiazua (2005) argued that youth restiveness can only be curbed through inclusiveness in policymaking, job creation, and improved living standards.

Regarding the setback in educational development, 377 respondents (mean = 3.64) agreed that insecurity has disrupted education across the South-East. One respondent reported:

Because of the sit-at-home order by IPOB and other criminal groups, my children couldn't complete their WAEC and NECO exams. Schools that defied the order were destroyed or burnt. Some parents relocated their children to Port Harcourt or Asaba, but others resorted to street hawking. This situation has created the second-highest number of out-of-school children after the North-East

(T. Amaka, personal communication, February 11, 2025).

This corroborates Hassan (2014), who found that armed struggle and insecurity cause school closures, disrupt academic calendars, and destroy school infrastructure, resulting in high dropout rates and "brain drain." Ukozor, Akuh, and Ahon (2024) added that many teachers and administrators in the South-East have been killed, while educational funds are diverted by corrupt politicians. Nejo (2021) also observed that the kidnapping and killing of teachers by armed groups have instilled fear in parents, compelling them to keep children at home. The combined effects include reduced manpower, lower enrolment, and the collapse of educational stability in the region.

Similarly, 341 respondents, with a mean score of 3.60, agreed that insecurity has caused mass migration and displacement. This finding supports Muhammed (2024), who noted that armed struggle in the South-East has created a cycle of displacement through violence and loss of livelihoods. Displaced persons often suffer exploitation, food insecurity, and humanitarian crises (Obinna, 2021). The destruction of farmlands and rural communities has disrupted trade, reduced agricultural output, and increased rural-to-urban migration.

As one interviewee explained:

More than three million people have fled the region. Many died while trying to escape, while others were detained indefinitely by security forces. This has worsened poverty and stifled development

(Y. Muhammed, personal communication, February 14, 2025).

According to Targba (2022), forced migration stems from conflicts, disasters, and poor socioeconomic conditions. He noted that violent conflict in Nigeria, particularly in the South-East has resulted in the mass displacement of people, worsening humanitarian and security conditions. Similarly, Giovetti (2019) defined forced migration as the involuntary movement of displaced persons within or across national borders.

Nwigwe (2022) emphasized that the enforcement of the sit-at-home order has induced fear and anxiety, crippling free movement and business activities. Onyema (2021, p.5) similarly observed that "the situation in the Southeast region has deteriorated to the extent that people fear for their lives and are skeptical about going out because of violent attacks and harassment." Such insecurity demobilizes human mobility and interaction, disrupting economic life across Igboland.

These acts of criminality have led to the wanton killing of entrepreneurs, community leaders, and professionals, thereby undermining regional productivity. Umeh (2023) affirmed that the death of business leaders and industrialists has weakened both local and national economies. The ongoing conflicts have also devastated agriculture, destroyed homes, and displaced entire communities.

Data further showed that 328 respondents, with a mean score of 3.54, agreed that insecurity has resulted in the death of many people in the South-East. Ukozor, Akuh, and Ahon (2024) reported that

kidnappings, ritual killings, political assassinations, and armed robbery have all escalated in the region.

One respondent remarked:

In Imo State alone, over 700 people have been killed; in Anambra, more than 500; in Abia, 220; in Enugu, 300; and in Ebonyi, about 120. Imo and Anambra remain the worst hit by IPOB-linked violence. The government must act proactively (J. Musa, personal communication, February 18, 2025).

The political dimension of armed struggle is also evident. Uche (2022) argued that the Biafran War reshaped the political consciousness of the Igbo, deepening nationalism and the quest for self-determination. Okwudiba (2019) contended that contemporary movements like IPOB are a resurgence of these sentiments, while Obinna (2022, p.8) noted that “most individuals kidnapped or killed in the Southeast are wealthy businessmen and politicians whose deaths or ransom payments destroy local economies.”

Despite minor variations in individual responses, data analysis revealed that 360 out of 389 respondents, along with all interviewees, agreed that armed struggle in the South-East has led to the proliferation of arms, economic stagnation, educational setbacks, displacement, political mobilization, and widespread loss of life. The state’s militarized response has, in turn, deepened cycles of repression, fear, and violent reprisal—thereby perpetuating insecurity in the region.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The findings of this study reveal that the relationship between armed struggle and insecurity in South-East Nigeria is complex, cyclical, and deeply rooted in historical, political, and socioeconomic grievances. The evidence shows that perceived political exclusion, economic marginalization, poor governance, and weak institutional response have sustained the region’s violent agitation. The emergence of groups such as IPOB and ESN is therefore not merely a product of ethnic nationalism but a response to decades of neglect, inequity, and mistrust in the Nigerian state.

The proliferation of arms, banditry, and militarized crackdowns have transformed the once economically vibrant region into one marked by fear, displacement, and socioeconomic stagnation. Educational development has suffered greatly, with frequent school closures and a rise in youth unemployment. The "sit-at-home" orders, while symbolic of defiance, have devastated trade, reduced productivity, and fractured social cohesion. Militarization as a state response has also worsened the situation, deepening resentment and radicalization among local communities.

It is evident that the pathway to sustainable peace and security in the South-East cannot be found through repression or force but through justice, inclusivity, and trust-building. A holistic approach that integrates political dialogue, socioeconomic empowerment, and institutional reform is required to break the cycle of armed struggle and insecurity.

Based on the above, the following recommendations are made:

1. **Promote Inclusive Political Dialogue:**
The Federal Government should initiate a structured dialogue with South-East stakeholders such as traditional rulers, youth leaders, civil society, and separatist sympathizers to address grievances peacefully. Genuine inclusion in governance and national decision-making will reduce the appeal of violent movements.
2. **Strengthen Socioeconomic Empowerment:**
Targeted economic interventions, youth employment programs, and infrastructure investment should be prioritized to rebuild livelihoods destroyed by insecurity. Special economic zones and small-business support can absorb unemployed youths vulnerable to recruitment by armed groups.
3. **Reform Security Operations:**
Security agencies must adopt intelligence-driven, community-based policing rather than militarized crackdowns. Human rights violations and arbitrary detentions fuel radicalization and must be replaced with trust-oriented peacekeeping strategies.
4. **Reconstruct Educational and Civic Institutions:**
Reopening and safeguarding schools in conflict zones should be a top priority. Civic education that promotes peace, tolerance, and national unity should be embedded in regional curricula to counter extremist narratives and rebuild social confidence.

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